

**THE SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK IN THE DELIVERY OF
BASIC EDUCATION SERVICES: THE CASE OF THE PUBLIC
ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THE SIXTH DISTRICT OF
THE PROVINCE OF PANGASINAN**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 4

Pages: 309-330

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2466

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13903938

Manuscript Accepted: 09-23-2024

The School-Based Management Framework in the Delivery of Basic Education Services: The Case of the Public Elementary Schools in the Sixth District of the Province of Pangasinan

Sanny A. Ferrer*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

School-Based Management (SBM) is the number 1 key reform thrust of the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) which underscores the empowerment of key stakeholders in school communities to enable them to actively participate in the continuous improvement of schools towards the attainment of higher pupil/student learning outcomes. This study sought to investigate the level of compliance to SBM framework of public elementary schools in the sixth congressional district in the province of Pangasinan and its impact on the delivery of basic education services in terms of school's key performance indicators for the school years 2017-2018, 2018-2019, and 2019-2020. This study employed the descriptive survey research design among 146 public elementary schools across ten municipalities in the district. The researcher used a survey form as the primary data gathering instrument which was derived from the SBM Assessment Tool of the Department of Education. Findings show that both the school heads and teachers perceived high compliance to the school-based management framework across the six dimensions of autonomy on school leadership, school improvement process, and school-based resources, of participation of internal and external stakeholders, and of accountability and transparency. However, perceived compliance is significantly higher for the teachers than their school heads. Enrollment across three school years was found to be significantly related to autonomy on school leadership. There was no significant relationship between the compliance to SBM framework principles and the learners' performance. However, in terms of teachers' performance, the number of produced instructional materials was correlated with autonomy on school-based resources. Higher compliance to autonomy on school-based resources was noted which implies higher production of instructional materials. In addition, the number of research outputs significantly influences the extent of participation of internal and external stakeholders. Furthermore, promotion rate and drop-out rate were positively and negatively, respectively, correlated with the school improvement process. This implies that a higher promotion rate and lower drop-out rate signify higher compliance to the school improvement process. Meanwhile, promotion rate, achievement rate in science, and the number of projects with LGU were positively correlated with the participation of stakeholders which influences higher participation. The drop-out rate was negatively correlated with accountability and transparency which implies that higher accountability influences lower drop-out rates. Thus, an intervention measure to improve the compliance to the SBM framework of public elementary schools was proposed which primarily considers the policy reforms, needs assessment, and allocation of resources in the planning, designing, developing, testing, implementing, and maintaining structural reforms to foster continuous innovation in public education.

Keywords: *school-based management, school performance*

Introduction

The public education system in the Philippines was established with the passage of the Education Act of 1901, otherwise known as Act No. 74 of the Philippine Commission. Although the Spanish regime attempted to establish an overall public school system and normal schools (Ecole normale), the American government saw the wisdom of setting up a centralized public school system in the country.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has been in existence for more than 100 years now—from its institutional beginnings as the Department of Public Instruction in 1901 to its constitution as a Department of Education in 1947, as the Department of Education and Culture in 1972, the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports in 1982, the Department of Education, Culture and Sports in 1987 and the Department of Education in 2001. Since 1995, this executive unit has been responsible for all levels of education. However, the legislated trifocalization of education in 1995 limited the scope of its mandate to basic education (elementary, secondary, and non-formal education).

From 1901 up to the present, the Philippine education system has been overwhelmed with perennial problems despite reform initiatives and projects instituted as early as the 1920s. It is still mired in difficult challenges that the bureaucracy has yet to address effectively such as high dropout rates, low participation rates, low performance in national achievement tests, and the shortage of facilities and teachers. But a common structural problem that has run through education reviews since the 1920s is the centralization of education.

The wave of decentralization spilled over to the education sector in the Philippines, which continued to have a centralized educational bureaucracy in the Philippines for most of the 20th century. The passage of Republic Act 9155 (An Act Instituting a Framework of Governance for Basic Education, Establishing Authority and Accountability, Renaming the Department of Education, Culture and Sports as the Department of Education, and for Other Purposes) provided the legal framework for decentralization.

The School-Based Management (SBM) was compliant from SY 2003-2004 to SY 2004-2005 in 23 school districts that participated in

the Third Elementary Education Project (TEEP) supported by the World Bank. The project provided funding for school infrastructure, training, curriculum development, and textbooks. SBM was introduced as an integrating framework for obtaining school-level project inputs and building school capacity for education planning and program implementation beginning in SY 2003-04. Schools participating in SBM were required to design a five-year School Improvement Plan (SIP) in partnership with parents and the community using data such as student achievement and students' learning needs assessments, with the school principal or head teacher leading the process. Based on the SIP, schools developed an Annual Implementation Plan (AIP) at the beginning of the school year and a report card to be shared with the community at the end of the school year. Project inputs for infrastructure, training, textbooks, and so forth, were partially based on the SIP. Principals and head teachers received training in leading the development and compliance to the SIP and the AIPs in collaboration with teachers and key members of the larger community. SBM schools also received funds for maintenance and operating expenses directly in cash rather than in kind, as had been the case previously. These cash funds could be used by the schools based on their AIP. The cash allocation was based on a formula that provided each school with a flat amount of funds plus a prorated figure based on the number of students and teachers as well as other criteria, such as the percentage of the indigenous student population in the school. Schools not participating in the SBM received no SBM-related training and no cash funds, and they were not required to develop SIPs and AIPs. The SBM training, funds, and requirements, such as the development of the SIP and AIP, were rolled out in three batches and eventually covered almost all (84%) of the 8,613 schools in the 23 project districts. The first batch comprised 1,666 schools in 2003-2004, largely because they were perceived to be more capable, although no explicit assignment mechanism was designed. The next batch of 2,700 schools was targeted for SBM rollout in 2004-2005, and another batch of 1,529 was included in 2005- 2006 (Ling, Khattri, & Jha, 2010)

The SBM program was designed to improve student outcomes through two main venues: by empowering the school community to identify education priorities and to allocate the school maintenance and operating budgets to those priorities (such as curriculum enrichment programs); and by enhancing transparency and accountability through the annual implementation plan and school report cards. However, the SBM program articulated no explicit assumptions regarding the timeframe within which improvements in student achievement were expected to take place. Systematic data on the level of uptake and compliance to the key features of the reforms are also not available.

Three years into its implementation, the Department of Education launched the SBM Manual of Assessment which evaluates the level of SBM practice of schools and identifies the level of assistance that the school needs. Specifically, the objectives of the assessment focus on determining the level of SBM practices of the school, provide the school a basis for the formulation of plans and strategies, improve the SBM support system of the school, and determine the effectiveness of SBM practices in the delivery of basic education services. To strengthen the support system of schools in implementing SBM, schools which fall under the established criteria – the number of enrollment and income class of municipality in which the school is located, DepEd established the so-called SBM Grant to augment the school's discretionary funds and improve their SBM standing.

From 1995 to 2009, only 14 studies utilized rigorous methods to assess the impact of SBM, and only six reported positive impacts on students' test scores (Patrinos, Barrera-Osorio, & Fasih, 2009). Eleven studies are country-specific from Latin America, one from Kenya, and two exploit data from multiple countries. No empirical evidence is available from East Asia. Since then, the studies focusing on school-based management have grown. Moreover, a study focusing on the impact of SBM on school performance has been limited. The study aims to add to the limited body of knowledge on school-based management.

Mostly, SBM studies in the Philippines focus on administrative performance and its relationship to schools' compliance with SBM. This study extends the focus to overall school performance using multiple variables that include the school infrastructure, the administrative head, teachers, and stakeholders. This draws from the assertion that to achieve a high level of compliance to SBM, the school should be able to utilize and leverage all of its resources – both tangible and intangible. Further, this study sought to investigate whether schools that efficiently and effectively use their resources are more likely to be able to actualize the intended objectives outlined by the Department of Education in the assessment of SBM framework principles.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of compliance to the school-based management framework principles in the delivery of basic education services among public elementary schools in the 6th Congressional District of Pangasinan. Specifically, it addressed the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents across the following variables?
 - 1.1. public elementary schools; and
 - 1.1.1. enrolment;
 - 1.1.2. number of classrooms;
 - 1.1.3. MOOE;
 - 1.1.4. sbm grant eligibility; and
 - 1.1.5. linkages established?
 - 1.2. school heads?
 - 1.2.1. highest educational attainment;

- 1.2.2. training and seminars attended related to SBM;
- 1.2.3. years in service as school head; and
- 1.2.4. number of years implementing the school-based management?
- 2. What is the level of compliance to SBM framework principles as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of the following indicators?
 - 2.1. autonomy;
 - 2.1.1. school leadership;
 - 2.1.2. school improvement process; and
 - 2.1.3. school-based resources?
 - 2.2. participation; and
 - 2.2.1. internal stakeholders; and
 - 2.2.2. external stakeholders?
 - 2.3. accountability and transparency?
- 3. Is there a significant difference between the perceived level of compliance to SBM framework principles by the teachers and school heads?
- 4. Is there a significant relationship between the following?
 - 4.1. profile of school head and level of compliance of SBM framework; and
 - 4.2. profile of school and level of compliance of SBM framework?
- 5. What is the level of performance of the public elementary schools for the past three school years (SY 2017-2018, SY 2018-2019, and SY 2019-2020) in terms of the following key performance indicators:
 - 5.1. learner’s performance;
 - 5.2. teacher’s performance;
 - 5.3. school performance;
 - 5.4. funds earned from IGP;
 - 5.5. projects with LGU; and
 - 5.6. awards received by the school?
- 6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of compliance of SBM framework principles and school performance?
- 7. What intervention program can be proposed to improve compliance to SBM Framework?

Methodology

Research Design

A research design is a structure or the blueprint of research that guides the process of research from the formulation of the research questions and hypotheses to reporting the research findings. The nature of the research questions and hypotheses, the variables involved, the sample of participants, the research settings, the data collection methods, and the data analysis methods are factors that contribute to the selection of the appropriate research design (Salkind, 2004).

This study employed the descriptive survey research design which involves a descriptive analysis of data gathered through a survey. The researcher used a survey form as the primary data gathering instrument where data were collected from at least a part of the population as the basis for assessing the incidence, distribution, and interrelations of phenomena and variables as they occur in the lives of people. (Bautista, 1998; Calmorin & Calmorin, 1996; Fraenkel & Wallen, 1993). The data collected were analyzed through descriptive research which involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes, tabulates, depicts, and describes the data collection (Glass & Hopkins, 1984).

Respondents

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Municipality	School Heads		Teachers	
	N	n	N	N (per school)
Asingan	19	12	298	36 (3)
Balungao	18	11	134	22 (2)
Natividad	18	11	126	22 (2)
Rosales	29	18	296	54 (3)
San Manuel	23	14	236	28 (2)
San Nicolas	31	20	238	40 (2)
San Quintin	16	10	191	30 (3)
Santa Maria	17	11	147	22 (2)
Tayug	17	11	230	33 (3)
Umingan	44	28	290	56 (2)
Grand Total	232	146	2186	343

Stratified random sampling was employed where each municipality under the 6th congressional district represents each stratum. From each stratum, a random sampling was made among the school heads and teachers.

There were two hundred thirty-two (232) public elementary schools across the ten municipalities in the congressional district, each represented by a school head. The number of respondents from each group was determined using Yamane's formula (1967:886).

Accordingly, at least 146 school heads from various schools in the congressional district were aimed to participate in the study. In addition, two or three teachers who come from the same school as the school heads, depending on the required sample size, also participated in the survey to duly represent their respective schools.

Instrument

Instrumentation refers to the tools or means by which investigators attempt to measure variables or items of interest in the data-collection process. It is related not only to instrument design, selection, construction, and assessment but also to the conditions under which the designated instruments are administered—the instrument is the device used by investigators for collecting data.

In this study, the researcher utilized a survey form as the primary data collection instrument. The questions were based on the DepEd SBM Assessment Tool. It is composed of three parts: (1) the profile of the school head; (2) the profile of the elementary school, and (3) the level of compliance to the SBM framework as perceived by the school head. Under the profile of the school head, the respondents were asked to identify their school names, educational attainments, some attended training and seminars relevant to SBM implementation, years in service as school heads, and years of compliance to SBM. Under the school profile, the respondents were asked to identify their school's enrolment counts across SY 2017-2018, 2018-2019, and 2019-2020, the number of classrooms, maintaining, operating, and other expenses (MOOE), SBM grant eligibility, and linkages established. Further, the respondents were asked to evaluate their level of compliance to the SBM framework along three dimensions of autonomy, participation, and accountability and transparency on a scale of 1 to 4, 4 being the highest and 1 the lowest. The level of compliance of the public elementary schools was also evaluated by teachers across each school.

Before the data collection proper, the validity and reliability of the researcher-made survey form were obtained. The form was content validated by experts and the results of the validity test conducted yielded Aiken's *V* value of greater than 0.70 across all dimensions (see Table 2) which affirms the validity of indicators used for the constructs in the survey instrument for SBM Principles (Dominguez-Lara, 2016). Meanwhile, the reliability of the survey form was assessed through pilot testing among 15 school heads and 39 teachers and the reliability analysis of the survey questionnaire yielded an Intraclass Correlation value of above 0.75 (see Table 3) which indicates that the coefficients are within the guidelines (Koo and Li, 2017). These acceptable validity and reliability results indicate that the instrument is a good measurement of the indicators involved.

Table 2. *Content Validity of Survey Questionnaire*

<i>SBM Principle</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>Aiken's V</i>
Autonomy: School Leadership	10	0.850
Autonomy: School Improvement Process	8	0.863
Autonomy: School-Based Resources	5	0.763
Participation: Internal Stakeholders	17	0.833
Participation: External Stakeholders	8	0.856
Accountability and Transparency	13	0.856

Table 3. *Reliability Analysis of Survey Questionnaire*

<i>SBM Principle</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>ICC Value</i>
Autonomy: School Leadership	10	0.936
Autonomy: School Improvement Process	8	0.966
Autonomy: School-Based Resources	5	0.856
Participation: Internal Stakeholders	17	0.955
Participation: External Stakeholders	8	0.901
Accountability and Transparency	13	0.961

Due to the pandemic, the survey was administered through Google Forms. The link was sent to the school heads' email addresses. Thus, the directory of the email addresses of the school heads was needed. Google Forms automatically logged the responses of the respondents. Guidelines to ensure the clarity of a survey were observed to get accurate answers from the respondents. Upon the culmination of data collection, the collected data was cleaned and exported into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The profile of the public elementary schools and school heads, as well as the school key performance indicators, were presented using frequency counts and percentages.

The indicators of the dimensions were rated using a four-point Likert-scale rating. The means of each indicator were calculated and

interpreted given the descriptive equivalents in Table 4. These were used in the succeeding parts of the study to describe the level of compliance of the respondents to the SBM framework.

Table 4. *Descriptive Ratings of Responses to SBM Principles*

<i>Numerical Values</i>	<i>Statistical Limits</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalents (DE)</i>
4	3.51-4.00	Highly Compliant
3	2.51-3.50	Moderately Compliant
2	1.51-2.50	Fairly Compliant
1	1.00-1.50	Not Compliant

For the difference in the level of compliance to the SBM framework between school heads and teachers, the independent samples t-test was used. The significance of the mean difference was set at a 0.05 level of significance. If the significance (or, p-value) of the mean difference is below the set threshold of .05, then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there was a significant difference between the two groups. Otherwise, there is no significant difference.

The relationships between the profile of the public school and the school heads and the level of compliance to the SBM framework were investigated using the chi-square test of independence. The relationship between the level of compliance to the SBM framework and school performance was also measured using the chi-square test.

The significance of the relationship was set at a 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, If the significance (or, p-value) of the relationship is below the set threshold of .05, then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there was a significant relationship between the variables. Otherwise, there is none.

Ethical Considerations

Survey ethics encompasses a set of ethical procedures that are intended to guide all survey researchers. These procedures were essential to the research process so that explicit care is taken that (a) no harm is done to any survey respondent, and (b) no survey respondent is unduly pressured or made to feel obligated to participate in a survey.

Based on the information provided by the researcher, potential respondents made an informed determination to their willingness to participate in the study (i.e., give their consent). In addition to the willingness to participate, it is fundamental that potential respondents have the competence to understand why the study is being conducted and what their rights and responsibilities are as respondents to participate. Participation was completely voluntary and the participants were also given the legal capacity to consent. The respondents were fully informed of the nature and duration of the research.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study. The presentation and discussion of the results are following the research questions. Data are presented both in tabular and textual formats.

Profile Of The School And School Heads

The profile of the school included in this study are enrolment, the number of classrooms, MOOE, SBM grant eligibility, and linkages established while the profile of the school heads includes highest educational attainment, training and seminars attended related to SBM, years in service as school head, and the number of years implementing the SBM practices.

Profile Of Elementary Schools

Enrolment: Findings presented in Table 5 show that the same percentage of schools (52.05%) has an enrolment count of 101 to 250 students for both SY 2017-2018 and SY 2018-2019. Meanwhile, for SY 2019-2020, a greater percentage of schools (55.48%) have an enrolment count of 101-250. It could be deduced that the schools are somehow maintaining their enrolment for the past three school years.

Number of Classrooms. Findings show that 57.53% of the elementary schools had around 6-10 classrooms. This implies that there is at least one classroom allotted to each of the six grade levels of the school.

Monthly MOOE. It is observed that all the schools receive at least Php11,000 monthly maintaining and operating expenses. More than half (52.74%) of the elementary schools get an MOOE from Php21,000 to 30,000 per month.

SBM Grant Eligibility. Among the 146 public elementary schools surveyed, findings show that most of them were not granted SBM grants. Before a school is given an SBM eligibility, it must belong to the schools with the highest number of dropouts with approved School Grant Proposals as reflected in the SIP/AIP, subject to criteria of the Guidelines for School-Based Management (SBM) Grants (DepEd Order No. 11, s. 2011) taking into account other fund sources for schools (e.g., nationally-funded programs, foreign-assisted projects, special education fund, congressional allocation, private sector donations, non-government organizations). This implies that most of the schools have low percentages of dropouts.

Linkages Established. Most of the schools (42.47%) have 1-2 projects with LGU. Meanwhile, 65 schools (44.52%) have partnered with 2-3 agencies where most (41.10%) are public ones. These findings seem to suggest that the schools through their heads are familiar with the importance of partners in the delivery of services to their constituents.

Table 5. Profile of the Public Elementary Schools

		Frequency	Percentage
Enrollment 2017-2018	At most 100 students	25	17.12%
	101-250 students	76	52.05%
	251-500 students	34	23.29%
	More than 500 students	11	7.53%
Enrollment 2018-2019	At most 100 students	25	17.12%
	101-250 students	76	52.05%
	251-500 students	33	22.60%
	More than 500 students	12	8.22%
Enrollment 2019-2020	At most 100 students	22	15.07%
	101-250 students	81	55.48%
	251-500 students	31	21.23%
	More than 500 students	12	8.22%
Number of Classrooms	1-5 classrooms	17	11.64%
	6-10 classrooms	84	57.53%
	11-15 classrooms	25	17.12%
	More than 15	20	13.70%
MOOE	Below Php11,000	0	0.00%
	Php11,000 to Php20,000	36	24.66%
	Php21,000 to Php30,000	77	52.74%
	More than Php30,000	33	22.60%
SBM Grant Eligibility	Yes	48	32.88%
	No	56	38.36%
	Not Sure	42	28.77%
Number of Projects with LGU	1-2 Projects	62	42.47%
	3-4 Projects	42	28.77%
	5-6 Projects	27	18.49%
	More than 6	15	10.27%
Number of Partner Agencies	0-1 agencies	56	38.36%
	2-3 agencies	65	44.52%
	More than 3	25	17.12%
Type of Partner Agencies	Public	60	41.10%
	Private	40	27.40%
	Both Public and Private	46	31.51%

Profile of School Heads

Highest Educational Attainment. Findings presented in Table 6 show that most (31.51%) school heads obtained Doctorate units. However, it must also be noted that a large percentage of them have completed either Master’s degree unit-earners or degree holders. This implies that the school heads are giving primary efforts to pursue and grow professionally by attending advanced studies.

Table 6. Profile of the School Head-Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	3	2.05%
	Master's Units	35	23.97%
	Master's Degree	42	28.77%
	Doctorate Units	46	31.51%
	Doctorate Degree	20	13.70%
SBM Related Training/Seminar	0-1 trainings	32	21.92%
	2-3 trainings	84	57.53%
	4-5 trainings	21	14.38%
	More than 5	9	6.16%
Years in Service as School Head	0-5 years	59	40.41%
	6-10 years	40	27.40%
	11-15 years	29	19.86%
	More than 15 years	18	12.33%
Years of Compliance to SBM	0-5 years	100	68.49%
	6-10 years	36	24.66%
	11-15 years	6	4.11%
	More than 15 years	4	2.74%

Training and Seminars Attended Related to SBM. Results also show that only 21.92% of the school heads have attended zero to one training while the rest have attended more than one training/seminar related to SBM which prepares them to implement the SBM framework in their respective schools. Attendance to said training may provide them the necessary preparation and information to implement the SBM framework.

Years in Service as School Head. Most of the school heads (68.49%) have been in service for at most five years. Meanwhile, only a handful of them is serving as school heads for 11 to 15 years (4.11%) and more than 15 years (2.74%).

Number of Years Implementing SBM. Table 6 also shows that the majority (68.65%) of the respondents have been implementing the SBM for at most five years. Only 2.7% of them reported that they have been implementing SBM in their schools for more than 15 years.

Level Of Compliance To SBM Framework

This section includes the extent of compliance of the selected public elementary school to the SBM framework. The dimensions of the SBM framework considered in this study are autonomy (school leadership, school improvement process, and school-based resources), participation (external and internal stakeholders), and accountability and transparency.

Autonomy on School Leadership

Table 7 shows the level of compliance to the SBM framework principle of autonomy in terms of school leadership. Findings reveal that school heads are highly compliant in all indicators of compliance to school leadership autonomy. However, we can notice that, despite both perceived as highly compliant, the teachers have shown a greater extent of compliance of their school heads than the school heads themselves. This implies that the teachers believe that their school heads are portraying high compliance to the SBM framework of autonomy on school leadership.

Table 7. Level of Compliance to School-Based Management (SBM) Principle of Autonomy in terms of School Leadership

	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
Demonstrates trustworthiness by protecting sensitive or confidential information, following required procedures, and honoring one's commitment to others or the organization.	3.82	Highly Compliant	3.89	Highly Compliant
Acts under a defined sense of right and wrong, but may allow situational factors to influence one's judgment.	3.64	Highly Compliant	3.78	Highly Compliant
Identifies and differentiates ethical and moral principles and values from unethical or dishonest behaviors.	3.79	Highly Compliant	3.87	Highly Compliant
Takes responsibility for own actions.	3.84	Highly Compliant	3.87	Highly Compliant
Discusses ethical implications of professional work and recognizes limits of own ethical knowledge.	3.77	Highly Compliant	3.80	Highly Compliant
Acts as a good steward of all public resources ensuring their efficient and effective use and maintenance.	3.80	Highly Compliant	3.86	Highly Compliant
Avoids spreading gossip, rumor, and false information.	3.81	Highly Compliant	3.86	Highly Compliant
Takes on a fair share of the work and acknowledges others to whom credit is due.	3.79	Highly Compliant	3.82	Highly Compliant
Demonstrates honesty consistently in all situations or conditions.	3.84	Highly Compliant	3.88	Highly Compliant
Takes independent action to correct situations that conflict with professional values.	3.73	Highly Compliant	3.81	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.79	Highly Compliant	3.84	Highly Compliant

The public elementary schools in the district benefit from exemplary school leadership skills and capacitated school heads essentially for SBM implementation. This is in adherence to the findings made by World Bank and Australian Aid (2016) which has shown that school leadership is a key explanatory factor for differences in performance among schools. Similarly, the study of Lubrica et al. (2019) reiterated the important role of the school heads on the impact of school leadership in SBM implementation in Benguet public secondary schools. Thus, it is expected that public elementary schools in the Sixth Congressional District will perform better in terms of key performance indicators when compared to other public elementary schools in other districts owing to strong school leadership.

Autonomy on School Improvement Process

It can be gleaned in Table 8 the level of compliance of school heads to autonomy on the school improvement process. It can be seen that the school heads perceived themselves to be most compliant in having the same level of involvement in the implementation and monitoring of the SIP/AIP whereas the teachers perceived their school heads to be most compliant in terms of regularly tracking, reporting, and updating and revising of SIP/AIP. Overall, we can notice that, despite both perceived as highly compliant, the teachers have shown a greater extent of compliance of their school heads than the school heads themselves. This implies that the teachers believe that their school heads are portraying high compliance to the SBM framework of autonomy on the school improvement process.

Table 8. *Level of Compliance to School-Based Management (SBM) Principle of Autonomy in terms of School Improvement Process*

	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
The school independently conducts an assessment of SBM practices.	3.45	Moderately Compliant	3.78	Highly Compliant
The school has mechanisms in place to sustain a continuous school improvement process.	3.65	Highly Compliant	3.81	Highly Compliant
The school governing council is involved in identifying projects and developing policies.	3.56	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant
The SIP/AIP are regularly tracked, reported, and updated/revised for continuous school improvement.	3.63	Highly Compliant	3.83	Highly Compliant
School improvement plan (SIP) and annual implementation plan (AIP) are formulated with engagement among stakeholders	3.70	Highly Compliant	3.81	Highly Compliant
Stakeholders have the same level of involvement as the school heads and teachers in the implementation and monitoring of the SIP/AIP.	3.52	Highly Compliant	3.68	Highly Compliant
School heads and teachers have the same level of involvement as stakeholders in the implementation and monitoring of the SIP/AIP.	3.72	Highly Compliant	3.75	Highly Compliant
The school improvement process includes performance-based incentives and rewards system for students and teachers as crucial components	3.66	Highly Compliant	3.76	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.61	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant

The results show that the public elementary schools in the Sixth Congressional District implement policies and establish mechanisms that strengthen school improvement planning. The results are evidence of the effectiveness of the guidelines Compliant by DepEd in 2015 which aimed at strengthening school improvement planning. As asserted by Lubrica et al. (2019), these results are a reflection of the importance of the school head in the school improvement process with emphasis on high expectations, quality teaching, and concern for students.

However, it must be noted the school heads assessed themselves as moderately compliant in terms of independent conduct assessment of SBM practices but were assessed to be highly compliant by the teachers. This supports the findings made by World Bank and Australian Aid (2016) in which school principals cited weakness in school improvement planning as an issue preventing compliance to SBM. Further, it follows the findings made by Chavez and Doromal (2018) in which results in a similar area point to a need in developing structures that introduce and sustain continuous improvement processes to integrate wider community participation and improve performance significantly.

Autonomy on School-Based Resources

Table 9 below shows the level of compliance of the school heads to the SBM framework of autonomy on school-based resources. It can be seen that both teachers generally perceived high compliance to autonomy on school-based resources. However, despite both assumed highly compliant, teachers showed a greater extent of school heads’ compliance than the school heads themselves. This implies that the teachers believe that their school heads are portraying high compliance to the SBM framework of autonomy on school-based resources.

Table 9. *Level of Compliance to School-Based Management (SBM) Principle of Autonomy in terms of School-Based Resources*

	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
The school’s funds are adequate.	3.41	Moderately Compliant	3.63	Highly Compliant
The school’s annual budget enabled the school to meet its annual performance targets.	3.41	Moderately Compliant	3.68	Highly Compliant
The school has substantial control over its finances.	3.64	Highly Compliant	3.73	Highly Compliant
The school is given due consideration and ample opportunity to fully utilize its funds.	3.76	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant
The school’s allocation is optimally utilized and disbursement of funds is aligned to SIP/AIP/ASB and recorded, reported, and accounted for.	3.76	Highly Compliant	3.82	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.60	Highly Compliant	3.74	Highly Compliant

Further, findings show that the school heads were moderately compliant to the adequacy of school funds and to the enabling of the annual budget to meet annual performance targets but were disagreed by the teachers where they perceived these to be highly compliant. On the other hand, both the school heads and the teachers perceived the highest level of compliance on the optimum utilization of the school’s allocation and alignment of disbursement to SIP/AIP/ASB.

This implies that the public elementary schools can optimize and allocate their resources despite weaknesses in fund adequacy and budget allocation for meeting performance targets as evidenced by the agreement of teachers and school heads in terms of adequacy of funds. The weaknesses uncovered are in support of the results of the 2016 Australian Aid and World Bank study wherein principals cited raising sufficient resources as a major impediment to putting SBM into practice. Despite this, Ecija (2020) asserted that the

monthly MOOE was highly utilized for access to complete basic education which can be the balancing factor in keeping high-level compliance to the SBM principle of autonomy on school-based resources.

Participation of Internal Stakeholders

Table 10 presents the results of the level of compliance to the SBM framework principle of participation of internal stakeholders. Overall, teachers evaluated the level of compliance of their school heads in terms of participation of internal stakeholders higher than the school heads themselves. This implies that the school heads are perceived by the teachers to be highly encouraging the internal stakeholders (i.e., the pupils and teachers) to participate in school activities.

Among the 17 indicators involved, the school heads and the teachers agree that they are most compliant with the idea that teachers are aware of their rights as primary internal stakeholders. The findings indicate that teachers, parents, and pupils are all considered and encouraged to engage in SBM implementation. This is in conjunction with the study of Lubrica et al. (2019) which also showed that the public elementary school heads are committed to working with both teachers and students for them to have the most informed and credible opinions as to what educational arrangements will be most beneficial.

Table 10. *Level of Compliance to SBM Principle of Participation of Internal Stakeholders*

	School Heads		Teachers	
	WM	DE	WM	DE
The pupils are aware of their rights as primary stakeholders.	3.59	Highly Compliant	3.72	Highly Compliant
Pupils are encouraged to engage in the formulation of SIP/AIP.	3.53	Highly Compliant	3.70	Highly Compliant
The pupils' membership in organizations contribute to the improvement of learning	3.63	Highly Compliant	3.76	Highly Compliant
Pupils are highly concerned about meeting their performance standards	3.57	Highly Compliant	3.73	Highly Compliant
Parents are aware of their rights as primary stakeholders.	3.71	Highly Compliant	3.80	Highly Compliant
Parents are encouraged to engage in the formulation of SIP/AIP.	3.64	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant
Parents are informed of student performance in terms of learning and behavior.	3.79	Highly Compliant	3.87	Highly Compliant
Parents are organized and regularly conducts meetings on school improvements.	3.58	Highly Compliant	3.72	Highly Compliant
Teachers are aware of their rights as primary stakeholders	3.80	Highly Compliant	3.90	Highly Compliant
Teachers maintain active membership in their association.	3.77	Highly Compliant	3.91	Highly Compliant
Teachers discuss with students and their parents the status of their performance	3.77	Highly Compliant	3.88	Highly Compliant
Teachers are encouraged to engage in the formulation of SIP/AIP.	3.77	Highly Compliant	3.87	Highly Compliant
Teachers of the school can conveniently pursue and continue professional development.	3.75	Highly Compliant	3.88	Highly Compliant
Teachers are should be fully accountable for meeting student performance	3.77	Highly Compliant	3.86	Highly Compliant
Teachers devote themselves to knowledge enrichment through regular training	3.75	Highly Compliant	3.88	Highly Compliant
Parents regularly report to the teachers learning process of pupils at home	3.55	Highly Compliant	3.70	Highly Compliant
Parents of the pupils are accepting accountability in instances of poor performance.	3.58	Highly Compliant	3.72	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.70	Highly Compliant	3.81	Highly Compliant

This is also in concordance with the findings made by Cabardo (2016) of the high level of participation among teachers in different school-initiated activities and the compliance to school-based management. This affirms the assertion of Martin (2019) of the vital role teachers play in decision-making and evidence of a democratic and participative system adopted by public elementary school heads in the Sixth Congressional District.

Participation of External Stakeholders

Table 10.1 presents the level of compliance of school heads to the principle of participation of external stakeholders. Overall, it must be noted that the teachers have shown a greater perceived level of compliance of their school heads which implies that the teachers observed high compliance of their school heads along with the participation of external stakeholders.

Nonetheless, both perceived a high extent of compliance of school heads. This indicates that compliance to SBM is effective in maintaining external stakeholder engagement indicative of public elementary schools' commitment.

Further, it is also emphasized by Bucud (2017) that ensuring the participation of competent external stakeholders that can productively engage and contribute to school management in a decentralized education environment is a manifestation of the awareness of the significance and impact of community capacity and culture on school-based management.

This also aligns with the assertion of Allawan (2012) on the importance of strengthening community linkages for the schools' goals to be ultimately realized.

Table 10.1 Level of Compliance to SBM Principle of Participation of External Stakeholders

	<i>School Heads</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>
The school maintains an active partnership with the local organizations.	3.65	Highly Compliant	3.83	Highly Compliant
Representatives from the municipal government regularly participate in meetings and consultations.	3.26	Moderately Compliant	3.59	Highly Compliant
The community should share accountability and responsibility in students' learning outcomes	3.59	Highly Compliant	3.76	Highly Compliant
The school should prioritize maintaining partnerships with outside groups.	3.59	Highly Compliant	3.69	Highly Compliant
External stakeholders actively involve themselves in the formulation of school improvement and annual implementation plans.	3.51	Moderately Compliant	3.70	Highly Compliant
The school enjoys receives strong support from the local government stakeholders.	3.59	Highly Compliant	3.77	Highly Compliant
Meetings and consultations with representatives from local organizations are conducted regularly.	3.43	Moderately Compliant	3.64	Highly Compliant
Conducted at least four (4) meetings for the school year	3.74	Highly Compliant	3.82	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.57	Highly Compliant	3.73	Highly Compliant

While holistically, external stakeholder participation is highly Compliant, results indicate that the public elementary schools may reflect an issue in terms of municipal government level participation as it was perceived as a moderate level of compliance. This supports the report made by the Bureau of Local Government Finance in 2012 which showed that local government education support is unevenly distributed across regions and is highly inequitable.

Accountability and Transparency

Shown in Table 11 is the perception of the school heads and teachers on the level of compliance of the school heads to accountability and transparency practices.

As a whole, both the school heads and the teachers were highly compliant. This implies that public elementary schools adhere to the SBM principles of accountability and transparency which shows their commitment to making sure the school decision-making process is transparent and the information that the school provides to its stakeholders is complete and accurate. Further, this shows that the school values transparency as an integral element of communication in public elementary schools. The results can be a better reflection of the level of commitment public elementary schools to observing and implementing practices that reflect accountability and transparency than of how effective the measures the public elementary schools are in projecting accountability and transparency. Should the results be interpreted in the context of the latter statement, this will be in disagreement with most findings on the SBM principle of accountability and transparency in the Philippines where parents' positive reaction towards the responsiveness of the schools and the presence of feedback channels despite the limited provision of information (Australian Aid and World Bank, 2016; Ecija, 2020).

Table 11. Level of Compliance to School-Based Management (SBM) Principle of Accountability and Transparency

	<i>School Heads</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>
The information on the school's bulletin board can reach beyond the school's confines and reach its stakeholders.	3.68	Highly Compliant	3.78	Highly Compliant
The school's monitoring and evaluation system seamlessly integrates the school's various reportorial requirements.	3.60	Highly Compliant	3.80	Highly Compliant
The school's monitoring and evaluation system allows full participation of stakeholders in the process	3.64	Highly Compliant	3.82	Highly Compliant
The school posts validated school performance in places where it can be easily accessible to anyone.	3.68	Highly Compliant	3.82	Highly Compliant
The school's monitoring and evaluation system includes tracking improvement in student performance indicators per class, per student, per subject.	3.69	Highly Compliant	3.84	Highly Compliant
The school's monitoring and evaluation system includes tracking of improvement in teacher performance.	3.68	Highly Compliant	3.85	Highly Compliant
The school's monitoring and evaluation system includes tracking of improvement in key performance indicators for school performance.	3.65	Highly Compliant	3.83	Highly Compliant
The school has mechanisms in place for parents and other stakeholders to provide feedback.	3.68	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant

	<i>School Heads</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>
Student learning outcomes and other performance indicators are disseminated on a school-wide basis.	3.66	Highly Compliant	3.78	Highly Compliant
A proper system is in place for formally handling complaints from each stakeholder group.	3.62	Highly Compliant	3.78	Highly Compliant
Students are briefed and counseled in case of learning and behavioral performance issues.	3.69	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant
The school's stakeholders champion the exercise of transparency and accountability for school performance.	3.73	Highly Compliant	3.82	Highly Compliant
The school is ready in case other schools conduct benchmarking activities with them.	3.55	Highly Compliant	3.77	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.67	Highly Compliant	3.80	Highly Compliant

Summary of Level of Compliance to SBM Framework

Reflected in Table 12 is the summary of the level of compliance of school heads to the SBM framework. It can be noticed that both groups have portrayed high compliance of school heads along the six dimensions of the SBM framework. This denotes that they perceived such compliance similarly. Further, the results indicate that the two groups diverge on the level of implementation in almost all of the SBM principles. This is in agreement with the findings of Yau and Cheng (2014), who uncovered significant differences between the perceptions of principals and teachers towards the areas of SBM in Hong Kong.

Table 12. Summary of Level of Compliance to SBM Principles

<i>SBM Principle</i>	<i>School Head</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>
Autonomy: School Leadership	3.79	Highly Compliant	3.84	Highly Compliant
Autonomy: School Improvement Process	3.61	Highly Compliant	3.79	Highly Compliant
Autonomy: School-based Resources	3.60	Highly Compliant	3.74	Highly Compliant
Participation: Internal Stakeholders	3.70	Highly Compliant	3.81	Highly Compliant
Participation: External Stakeholders	3.57	Highly Compliant	3.73	Highly Compliant
Accountability and Transparency	3.67	Highly Compliant	3.80	Highly Compliant
Overall	3.64	Highly Compliant	3.78	Highly Compliant

However, it must be noted that the teachers showed higher extents of perceived compliance of the school heads than the school heads themselves. This illustrates that teachers are more likely to have a better perception of compliance to the SBM principles than the school heads. This is reflected in the study of Martin (2019) which has shown teachers to have a better assessment of SBM implementation than the school heads. This can be interpreted though unsubstantiated that school heads are more objective in assessing the level of implementation than the teachers as they have more information available to gauge the status of SBM compliance of their respective public elementary schools. Teachers, on the other hand, showed a higher perception of the level of compliance to the SBM principles which implies that they put their confidence on their respective school heads in terms of ensuring the compliance of their schools to SBM principles.

Comparison of the Perceived Level of Compliance to SBM Framework Between School Heads and the Teachers

Based on the initial findings, the school heads and the teachers perceived a similar extent of compliance along the six dimensions of the SBM framework, an independent t-test was performed to statistically compare their mean responses. Results are shown in Table 13 below.

Findings show that there were negative mean differences between the school heads and the teachers which imply that school teachers gave higher average ratings than the school heads for all the six principles of the SBM framework. Further, almost all of these mean differences were statistically significantly different, except in terms of autonomy on school leadership.

The non-significant difference between the school heads and the teachers in terms of school leadership implies that they perceived such high compliance similarly. This means that the school heads and teachers do not differ in their perception of the level of compliance of the school heads to the SBM framework on school leadership practices.

However, this goes against Conley (1993) who found a significant difference between the perception of the teachers and school heads on the level of compliance to the SBM framework of the school heads. In his recent study, Conley (2013) stated that SBM is more of an enabling mechanism for other goals to materialize.

Table 13. *Difference in the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework between the Teachers and School Heads*

Variables	Compared Groups	Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Decision
Autonomy: School Leadership	School Heads	3.79	-0.05	-1.064	.305	Not Significant
	Teachers	3.84				
Autonomy: School Improvement	School Heads	3.61	-0.18	-3.745	.002	Significant
	Teachers	3.79				
Autonomy: School-based Resources	School Heads	3.60	-0.14	-2.595	.020	Significant
	Teachers	3.74				
Participation: Internal Stakeholders	School Heads	3.70	-0.11	-2.160	.049	Significant
	Teachers	3.81				
Participation: External Stakeholders	School Heads	3.57	-0.16	-2.640	.019	Significant
	Teachers	3.73				
Accountability and Transparency	School Heads	3.67	-0.13	-2.434	.028	Significant
	Teachers	3.80				

*Mean Difference = School Heads – Teachers

Meanwhile, there were significant negative mean differences in the perceived level of compliance to the principles of autonomy on the school improvement process and school-based resources, participation of internal and external stakeholders, and accountability and accessibility between that school heads and the teachers. Similarly, this implies that the teachers showed a greater extent of perceived compliance to these SBM practices than the school heads. This can be explained by the fact that governance, teacher leadership, personnel structures, working relationships, and school improvement processes were also perceived as differences between and among the teachers and school heads (Oswald, 2019).

Relationship Between the Profile of School and School Heads and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework

This section involves the test of the relationship between the profiles of the public elementary schools and school heads and the level of compliance to the SBM framework.

Relationship between School Profile and Compliance to SBM Framework

This section shows the significant relationships between the profile and compliance to the SBM framework of the public elementary schools.

Findings show that enrolment across the past three school years was significantly associated with compliance with school leadership. This implies that schools that maintain their enrolment counts between 101-250 tend to be highly compliant to autonomy on school leadership. However, compliance with all other SBM principles was found to be not significantly associated with enrolment across the three school years.

As reported by Pont et al. (2008), school heads and principals tend to have many frustrations brought about by stress and they constantly feel that they are unable to achieve all their tasks and responsibilities when student enrolments drop. Such stress may diminish the principals’ ability to do their best work and over time it can erode their commitment to the job. Hence, the increasing number of enrolled pupils prompted the school heads to exercise their leadership role to lead and provide quality education to their pupils.

Table 14a. *Significant Relationship Between the Enrolment and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		x2-value	p-value	Interpretation
Enrolment (SY 2017-18)	School Leadership	7.379	0.025	Significant
	School Improvement Process	4.290	0.117	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	4.283	0.117	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	4.366	0.113	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	0.927	0.629	Not Significant
Enrolment (SY 2018-19)	Accountability and Transparency	3.118	0.210	Not Significant
	School Leadership	7.379	0.025	Significant
	School Improvement Process	2.354	0.308	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	1.508	0.471	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	1.183	0.553	Not Significant
Enrolment (SY 2019-20)	External Stakeholders	0.927	0.629	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	1.659	0.436	Not Significant
	School Leadership	9.084	0.011	Significant
	School Improvement Process	1.449	0.485	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	4.259	0.119	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	4.470	0.107	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	3.062	0.216	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	2.189	0.335	Not Significant

Table 14b. *Crosstabulation Between the Enrolment and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		School Leadership	
		Moderately Compliant	Highly Compliant
SY 2017-2018	At most 100 students	0	25
	101-250 students	17	59
	More than 250 students	6	39
SY 2018-2019	At most 100 students	0	25
	101-250 students	17	59
	More than 250 students	6	39
SY 2019-2020	At most 100 students	0	22
	101-250 students	19	62
	More than 250 students	4	39

Meanwhile, SBM grant eligibility was found to be significantly associated with autonomy to the school improvement process, participation of internal and external stakeholders, and accountability and transparency.

This suggests that an SBM grant-eligible school can exercise the principles of school improvement, encourage the participation of external and internal stakeholders, and practice accountability and transparency. As previously mentioned, eligibility to SBM grants signifies that the school has a high number of drop-out students relative to its enrolment number.

Moreover, most schools were not given SBM grants which imply that most schools have low percentages of drop-outs. Thus, non-eligibility to such a grant indicates high compliance of the schools to SBM framework principles, most especially in autonomy on the school improvement process, participation of internal and external stakeholders, and accountability.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship Between the SBM Grant Eligibility and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		<i>x</i> ² -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
SBM Grant Eligibility	School Leadership	0.484	0.785	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	8.307	0.016	Significant
	School-Based Resources	4.610	0.100	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	8.310	0.016	Significant
	External Stakeholders	8.971	0.011	Significant
Accountability and Transparency		8.315	0.016	Significant

Table 15.1 *Crosstabulation Between the SBM Grant Eligibility and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		SBM Grant Eligibility		
		Yes	No	Not Sure
School Improvement	Moderately Compliant	8	24	14
	Highly Compliant	40	32	28
Internal Stakeholders	Moderately Compliant	7	22	10
	Highly Compliant	41	34	32
External Stakeholders	Moderately Compliant	9	26	16
	Highly Compliant	39	30	26
Accountability	Moderately Compliant	8	24	13
	Highly Compliant	40	32	29

Further, the number of projects partnered with the local government unit is also associated with the participation of external stakeholders. This implies that observance or compliance to the principles of SBM on the participation of external stakeholders can lead to compliance to projects for the school.

According to the Australian Council for Educational Research (2013), “When partnerships are well-planned, sustainable, collaborative, and based on a mutual sharing of expertise, knowledge, resources, and skills, they are effective and can make an impact” (p. 106).

When different stakeholders recognize each other’s contributions and learnings and can collaborate to create quality and relevant programs, partnership outcomes improve.

Partnerships pave the way for industry-linked training and genuine employment options for learners, additional training resources for teachers, and a pool of well-trained workers for industry.

The LGUs also play a big role as partners and can help advocate for and mobilize other types of support such as arrange and manage job fairs and create on-the-job training and employment opportunities for learners and completers (EDC, 2017).

Table 16. Significant Relationship Between the Number of Projects with LGU and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework

		<i>x</i> ² -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Number of Projects with LGU	School Leadership	3.874	0.144	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	1.616	0.446	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	0.604	0.739	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	2.240	0.326	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	10.765	0.005	Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	3.200	0.202	Not Significant

Table 16.1 Crosstabulation Between the Enrolment and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework

		External Stakeholders	
		Moderately Compliant	Highly Compliant
Number of Projects with LGU	1-2 Projects	31	31
	3-4 Projects	10	32
	More than 4	10	32

However, the number of classrooms, MOOE, number of partner agencies, and types of partner agencies were not found to be significantly correlated with compliance with the SBM framework of the schools, as shown in Table 17.

Table 17. Significant Relationship Between the Number of Classrooms, MOOE, Number of Partner Agencies, Type of Partner Agencies, and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework

		<i>x</i> ² -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Number of Classrooms	School Leadership	3.867	0.145	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	0.587	0.746	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	4.246	0.120	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	2.339	0.310	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	0.887	0.642	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	2.003	0.367	Not Significant
MOOE	School Leadership	4.295	0.117	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	3.561	0.169	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	4.870	0.088	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	2.465	0.292	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	2.142	0.343	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	1.659	0.436	Not Significant
Number of Partner Agencies	School Leadership	0.337	0.845	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	0.824	0.662	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	0.644	0.725	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	0.786	0.675	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	3.033	0.220	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	2.622	0.270	Not Significant
Type of Partner Agencies	School Leadership	0.128	0.938	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	0.334	0.846	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	1.042	0.594	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	0.159	0.924	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	2.475	0.290	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	0.332	0.847	Not Significant

Relationship between School Heads Profile and Compliance to SBM Framework

This section shows the significant relationships between the profile of the school heads and their level of compliance to the SBM framework.

Table 18a shows that the number of years in service as school head was significantly correlated with school leadership and with accountability and transparency. This means that a school head's experience provided them the ability to practice the leadership principles and be accountable and transparent in their activities.

Moreover, those who have served for more years as school heads tend to exhibit higher compliance to leadership and accountability. As previously mentioned, school heads and principals tend to have many frustrations brought about by stress and they constantly feel that they are unable to achieve all their tasks and responsibilities as they serve longer (Pont et al., 2008). Further, as the length of service increases, the leadership aspirations are gradually met.

Table 18a. *Significant Relationship Between the Years in Service as School Head and Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		<i>x²-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Years in Service as School Head	School Leadership	12.234	0.002	Significant
	School Improvement Process	3.089	0.213	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	1.047	0.592	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	4.977	0.083	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	1.658	0.436	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	7.237	0.027	Significant

Table 18b. *Crosstabulation Between the Years in Service as School Head and Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		<i>Years as School Head</i>		
		<i>0-5 years</i>	<i>6-10 years</i>	<i>More than 10 years</i>
School Leadership	Moderately Implemented	8	24	14
	Highly Implemented	40	32	28
Accountability	Moderately Implemented	7	22	10
	Highly Implemented	41	34	32

Meanwhile, the number of years in implementing the SBM framework was associated with internal stakeholder’s participation, as shown in Table 19a. This means that a school head with long years in implementing the SBM framework principles can encourage the participation of the teachers and pupils in implementing the programs, projects, and activities of the school. Finding and engaging with your internal stakeholders is also crucial to making things happen. No company can implement the most impelling strategy without the involvement of its employees. "Highly engaged employees always go beyond mere compliance with organizational expectations. They strive to exceed expectations." (Rivenburgh, 2013). Because internal stakeholders do the work and their satisfaction is often given the greatest importance in judging the success of a strategy or project, stakeholder managers need to make sure that they identify all internal stakeholders.

However, educational attainment and training and seminars of the school heads were not found to be associated with their level of compliance to the SBM framework, as shown in Table 20.

Table 19a. *Significant Relationship Between the Years of Compliance to SBM and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		<i>x²-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Years of Compliance to SBM	School Leadership	0.735	0.391	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	0.334	0.563	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	1.806	0.179	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	5.290	0.021	Significant
	External Stakeholders	3.396	0.065	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	2.174	0.140	Not Significant

Table 19b. *Crosstabulation Between the Years of Compliance to SBM and the Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		<i>Internal Stakeholders</i>	
		<i>Moderately Compliant</i>	<i>Highly Compliant</i>
Years of Implementation of SBM	0-5 years	21	79
	More than 5 years	18	28

Table 20. *Significant Relationship Between the School Heads Profile and Level of Compliance to SBM Framework*

		<i>x²-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Highest Educational Attainment	School Leadership	1.000	0.769	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	2.115	0.549	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	0.045	0.997	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	0.129	0.988	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	4.155	0.245	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	1.142	0.767	Not Significant
SBM-Related Training and Seminars	School Leadership	0.513	0.474	Not Significant
	School Improvement Process	2.317	0.128	Not Significant
	School-Based Resources	0.163	0.686	Not Significant
	Internal Stakeholders	1.911	0.167	Not Significant
	External Stakeholders	0.042	0.837	Not Significant
	Accountability and Transparency	0.112	0.738	Not Significant

School Performance

School performances across the SY 2017-2018, 2018-2019, and 2019-2020 were measured along with several parameters: performance of learners, the performance of teachers, and the school's key performance indicators.

Performance of Learners

Table 21 presents the performance of learners in terms of numbers of awards and participation for the past three school years.

Awards. It can be noticed that there were similar numbers of awards for SY 2017-2018 and SY 2018-2019. Most of the schools have obtained student awards at most 10 awards in each school year and only a few have received more than 30 awards. However, the number of schools that received more than 30 student awards in a school year increased during the SY 2019-2020. This indicates that the level of the performance of the learners may increase the school performance as reflected in the increasing number of awards of the learners.

Participation in Festivals. Similarly, there were similar numbers of participation to festivals for SY 2017-2018 and SY 2018-2019. Most of the schools have participated in at most 10 festivals in each school year and only a few have attended more than 30. However, the number of schools that participated in more than 30 festivals in a school year increased during the SY 2019-2020. This indicates that the level of the performance of the learners may increase the school performance as reflected in the increasing number of participations to academic festivals.

Table 21. *Learners' Performance for the Past Three School Years*

		SY 2017-18		SY 2018-19		SY 2019-20	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Number of Awards in Contests	At most 10	61	41.78%	59	40.41%	69	47.26%
	11 to 20	41	28.08%	42	28.77%	23	15.75%
	21 to 30	21	14.38%	23	15.75%	19	13.01%
	More than 30	23	15.75%	22	15.07%	35	23.97%
Number of Participations in Festivals	At most 10	107	73.29%	108	73.97%	101	69.18%
	11 to 20	21	14.38%	21	14.38%	21	14.38%
	21 to 30	10	6.85%	9	6.16%	11	7.53%
	More than 30	8	5.48%	8	5.48%	13	8.90%

Performance of Teachers

Table 22 presents the performance of learners in terms of the numbers of instructional materials, research outputs, and awards received for the past three school years.

Table 22. *Teachers' Performance for the Past Three School Years*

		SY 2017-18		SY 2018-19		SY 2019-20	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Number of Instructional Materials	None	90	61.64%	91	62.33%	90	61.64%
	1-5	44	30.14%	43	29.45%	42	28.77%
	6-10	12	8.22%	12	8.22%	12	8.22%
	More than 10	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	1.37%
Number of Research Outputs	None	114	78.08%	119	81.51%	116	79.45%
	1-5	32	21.92%	25	17.12%	30	20.55%
	6-10	0	0.00%	1	0.68%	0	0.00%
	More than 10	0	0.00%	1	0.68%	0	0.00%
Number of Awards Received	None	30	20.55%	32	21.92%	34	23.29%
	1-5	85	58.22%	88	60.27%	82	56.16%
	6-10	18	12.33%	15	10.27%	17	11.64%
	More than 10	13	8.90%	11	7.53%	13	8.90%

Instructional Materials. It is sad to note that majority of the teaches have not prepared instructional materials during the three years. Most of the teachers who did have prepared one to five instructional materials during the past three years and nearly none have prepared more than ten materials. This implies that there was a lack of instructional materials among the teachers. Considering the importance of instructional materials, school heads shall encourage their teachers to produce instructional materials as an additional reference in teaching.

Research Outputs. Similarly, most of the teachers have not produced research outputs for the past three years. While most of those who did have produced one to five outputs, nearly none has produced more than ten research. This implies that the school heads must provide training to the teachers in the preparation and conduct of researches.

Awards Received. In terms of awards, most of the school heads claimed that most of the teachers consistently received one to five throughout the past three school years. While few schools reported having received more than 30 teacher awards, some schools claimed that they have not received any award at all.

School Key Performance Indicators

Table 23 presents the schools' key performance indicators for the last three school years.

Participation Rate. It is worth noting that almost all the schools have a participation rate of more than 95% and this number of schools with such excellent participation rate was increasing during the three years. Only a handful of them has below 75% participation rates. This means that almost all of the enrolled students for the past three years had participated.

Cohort Survival Rate. Most schools have more than a 95% cohort survival rate but the trend was fluctuating during the three years. Only a handful of them has below 75% cohort survival rates. This suggests that the percentage of enrollees at the starting grade level in a given school year who reached the final grade level of elementary education was satisfactorily high as observed in the past three years.

Completion Rate. Most schools have reached a more than 95% completion rate during the three years. Only a handful of them has below 75% completion rates which show that there are still pupils who could not complete their schooling.

Graduation Rate. A decreasing trend in the number of schools that have more than 95% graduation rate is registered and no school had below 75% graduation rate for the three years.

Promotion Rate. Almost all schools have a promotion rate of more than 95% and no school that have a promotion rate below 85%. This might be brought by the policy of the Department of Education on mass promotion.

Retention Rate. There was a decreasing trend in the number of schools that have a retention rate of more than 95% across the three years. Only a few schools have a below 75% retention rate during the later years.

Drop-out Rate. Notably, most schools have zero dropout rates. Though some schools have minimal dropout rates, the results show that the schools are implementing the policy of DepEd that no children should be left behind.

Table 23. Key Performance Indicators of Schools for the Past Three School Years

		SY 2017-18		SY 2018-19		SY 2019-20	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
Participation Rate	At most 75%	3	2.05%	3	2.05%	3	2.05%
	76% to 85%	10	6.85%	9	6.16%	9	6.16%
	86% to 95%	36	24.66%	35	23.97%	30	20.55%
	More than 95%	97	66.44%	99	67.81%	104	71.23%
Cohort Survival Rate	At most 75%	5	3.42%	9	6.16%	10	6.85%
	76% to 85%	16	10.86%	14	9.59%	11	7.53%
	86% to 95%	38	26.03%	37	25.34%	35	23.97%
	More than 95%	87	59.59%	86	58.90%	90	61.64%
Completion Rate	At most 75%	4	2.74%	8	5.48%	6	4.11%
	76% to 85%	11	7.53%	10	6.85%	9	6.16%
	86% to 95%	21	14.35%	19	13.01%	20	13.70%
	More than 95%	110	75.34%	109	74.66%	111	76.03%
Graduation Rate	At most 75%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	76% to 85%	1	0.68%	2	1.37%	2	1.37%
	86% to 95%	1	0.68%	4	2.74%	3	2.05%
	More than 95%	144	98.63%	140	95.98%	141	96.58%
Promotion Rate	At most 75%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
	76% to 85%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	1	0.68%
	86% to 95%	6	4.11%	8	5.48%	7	4.79%
	More than 95%	140	95.89%	138	94.52%	139	94.52%
Retention Rate	At most 75%	0	0.00%	1	0.68%	2	1.37%
	76% to 85%	2	1.37%	4	2.74%	7	4.79%
	86% to 95%	20	13.70%	17	11.64%	22	15.07%
	More than 95%	124	84.93%	124	84.93%	115	78.77%
Drop-out	0.00%	137	93.84%	124	84.93%	132	90.41%
	0.10% to 0.59%	2	1.37%	11	7.53%	7	4.79%
	0.60% to 1.00%	6	4.11%	5	3.42%	4	2.74%
	More than 1.00%	1	0.68%	6	4.11%	3	2.05%
Repetition Rate	0.00%	128	87.67%	118	80.82%	113	77.40%
	0.10% to 0.59%	5	3.42%	3	2.05%	2	1.37%
	0.60% to 1.00%	7	4.79%	13	8.90%	9	6.16%
	More than 1.00%	6	4.11%	12	8.22%	22	15.07%
Achievement Rate (English)	At most 75%	12	8.22%	13	8.90%	10	6.85%
	76% to 85%	90	61.64%	86	58.90%	85	58.22%
	86% to 95%	40	27.40%	43	29.45%	47	32.19%
	More than 95%	4	2.74%	4	2.74%	4	2.74%
Achievement Rate (Mathematics)	At most 75%	15	10.27%	13	8.90%	12	8.22%
	76% to 85%	87	59.59%	83	56.85%	82	56.16%
	86% to 95%	41	28.08%	48	32.88%	50	34.25%
	More than 95%	3	2.05%	2	1.37%	2	1.37%
Achievement Rate (Science)	At most 75%	15	10.27%	12	8.22%	10	6.85%
	76% to 85%	82	56.16%	87	59.59%	85	58.22%
	86% to 95%	46	31.51%	48	32.88%	48	32.88%
	More than 95%	3	2.05%	2	1.37%	3	2.05%
Achievement Rate (Overall)	At most 75%	13	8.90%	12	8.22%	9	6.16%
	76% to 85%	89	60.96%	84	57.53%	86	58.90%
	86% to 95%	40	27.40%	48	32.88%	49	33.56%
	More than 95%	4	2.74%	2	1.37%	2	1.37%
Funds Earned from IGP	None	130	89.04%	129	88.36%	121	82.88%
	1-5	2	1.37%	7	4.79%	6	4.11%
	6-10	9	6.16%	7	4.79%	11	7.53%
	More than 10	5	3.42%	3	2.05%	8	5.48%
Number of School Awards	None	21	14.38%	10	6.85%	28	19.18%
	1-5	112	76.71%	121	82.88%	106	72.60%
	6-10	9	6.16%	9	6.16%	5	3.42%
	More than 10	4	2.74%	6	4.11%	7	4.79%

Repetition Rate. Similarly, most schools claimed that they have zero repetition rates but there is a minimal number of schools that have more than a 1% repetition rate. This happened maybe because, despite the effort of teachers to tutor their pupils, there are still pupils who could not cope with the demands of school work.

Achievement Rate. The school heads claimed that they have achievement rates from 75% to more than 95%. The majority of the schools have a 76-85% achievement rate in English, Math, and Science and when taken it collectively.

Funds Earned from IGP. The majority of the schools have no funds from their IGP. A limited number of schools have earned funds from their IGP. This indicates that there are few schools with projects that will generate additional funds for the schools.

Number of Projects with the LGU. A bigger number of schools disclosed that they have 1-5 projects with the LGU and no schools have more than projects with the LGU for the three years.

School Award. All school heads claimed that their schools received around 1 to 5 awards for the three years. However, a big chunk of the schools hasn't received any school award during the three years.

Relationship Between the Compliance to SBM Framework and School Performance

The relationship between the compliance to the SBM framework and the school performance along learners, teachers, and the school as a whole was determined using the Pearson Product Moment of Coefficient of Correlation.

Compliance to SBM Framework and Learners' Performance

The relationship between the level of compliance to the SBM framework and the learners' performance can be seen in Table 19a below.

Table 24. Relationship Between Level of Compliance to SBM Framework and Learners' Performance

		Correlation		Interpretation
		r-value	p-value	
School	Contest Awards	-0.061	0.467	Not Significant
Leadership	Festival Participations	-0.011	0.896	Not Significant
School Improvement	Contest Awards	-0.070	0.398	Not Significant
	Festival Participations	-0.008	0.923	Not Significant
School Based Resources	Contest Awards	-0.040	0.636	Not Significant
	Festival Participations	0.041	0.620	Not Significant
Internal Stakeholders	Contest Awards	0.063	0.447	Not Significant
	Festival Participations	0.062	0.460	Not Significant
External Stakeholders	Contest Awards	-0.014	0.862	Not Significant
	Festival Participations	0.057	0.497	Not Significant
Accountability and Transparency	Contest Awards	-0.036	0.665	Not Significant
	Festival Participations	-0.004	0.962	Not Significant

Findings show that no significant relationship existed between the level of compliance to SBM framework principles and the learners' performance. Thus, the level of compliance to the SBM framework does not necessarily influence the performance of the learners.

Compliance to SBM Framework and Teachers' Performance

Table 24.1 below shows the relationship between the level of compliance to the SBM framework and teachers' performance.

Table 24.1 Relationship Between Level of Compliance to SBM Framework and Teachers' Performance

		Correlation		Interpretation
		r-value	p-value	
School	Instructional Materials	0.073	0.379	Not Significant
Leadership	Research Outputs	0.093	0.266	Not Significant
	Awards Received	0.108	0.194	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.085	0.305	Not Significant
School Improvement Process	Research Outputs	0.144	0.084	Not Significant
	Awards Received	0.005	0.948	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.181	0.028	Significant
School Based Resources	Research Outputs	0.158	0.057	Not Significant
	Awards Received	0.102	0.218	Not Significant
	Instructional Materials	0.154	0.063	Not Significant
Internal Stakeholders	Research Outputs	0.174	0.036	Significant
	Awards Received	0.119	0.151	Not Significant

External Stakeholders	Instructional Materials	0.124	0.137	Not Significant
	Research Outputs	0.210	0.011	Significant
	Awards Received	0.085	0.310	Not Significant
Accountability and Transparency	Instructional Materials	0.103	0.216	Not Significant
	Research Outputs	0.153	0.065	Not Significant
	Awards Received	0.086	0.300	Not Significant

Findings show that a significant relationship existed between the number of instructional materials prepared by the teachers and the level of compliance to school-based resources. The significant positive association means that a higher level of compliance to school-based resources implies a greater number of instructional materials produced by the teachers.

Moreover, the level of compliance to the participation of internal and external stakeholders was significantly correlated to the number of research outputs. This significant positive association implies that a higher level of compliance to the participation of internal and external stakeholders influences more research outputs of the teachers.

However, all the other principles were not found to be correlated with the teachers' performance.

Compliance to SBM Framework and Schools' Key Performance Indicators

Table 24.2 shows the results of the test of the relationship between compliance to SBM principles and school performance.

Findings show that compliance with the school improvement process was significantly positively correlated with the promotion rate. This implies that a higher level of compliance to the school improvement process indicates a higher promotion rate of schools. Meanwhile, it was also found to be negatively correlated with the drop-out rate. This implies that a higher level of compliance to the school improvement process indicates lower drop-out rates.

Moreover, there were significant positive correlations between the level of compliance to the participation of external stakeholders and promotion rates, achievement rates in science, and the number of LGU projects. These positive relationships indicate that a higher extent of compliance to the participation of external stakeholders influences a higher promotion rate, achievement rate in science, and the number of projects with LGU.

Table 24.2 Relationship Between Level of Compliance to SBM Framework and Schools' Key Performance Indicators

	SBM Principles											
	School Leadership		School Improvement		School-Based Resources		Internal Stakeholders		External Stakeholders		Accountability/ Transparency	
	R	p	R	p	R	p	R	p	R	p	R	p
Participation Rate	0.058	0.486	0.070	0.399	0.025	0.761	0.028	0.737	0.000	0.998	0.028	0.735
Cohort Survival Rate	0.049	0.560	0.070	0.401	0.065	0.436	0.065	0.439	0.079	0.345	0.062	0.459
Completion Rate	0.048	0.562	0.070	0.402	0.065	0.437	0.054	0.440	0.079	0.345	0.062	0.460
Graduation Rate	-0.041	0.619	0.041	0.626	0.016	0.849	-0.036	0.666	-0.034	0.685	0.022	0.790
Promotion Rate	0.050	0.548	.185*	0.026	0.082	0.326	0.138	0.095	.173*	0.037	0.152	0.068
Retention Rate	0.103	0.214	0.025	0.763	0.017	0.834	0.085	0.308	0.033	0.694	0.042	0.618
Drop-Out Rate	-0.131	0.166	-.186*	0.025	-0.148	0.075	-0.124	0.135	-0.112	0.180	-.172*	0.038
Repetition Rate	0.033	0.696	-0.096	0.249	0.041	0.620	-0.028	0.733	-0.034	0.680	-0.035	0.671
Achievement in English	0.044	0.599	-0.047	0.571	0.046	0.585	-0.029	0.727	0.055	0.511	0.011	0.894
Achievement in Math	0.072	0.391	-0.032	0.703	0.061	0.467	0.029	0.724	0.090	0.281	0.073	0.384
Achievement in Science	0.152	0.068	0.038	0.648	0.148	0.074	0.103	0.215	.165*	0.047	0.122	0.144
Overall Achievement	0.066	0.431	0.064	0.446	0.081	0.331	0.070	0.405	0.096	0.247	0.071	0.393
Funds from IGP	0.073	0.381	0.121	0.146	-0.016	0.851	0.083	0.319	0.095	0.255	0.102	0.219
LGU Projects	0.010	0.908	0.060	0.471	0.067	0.419	0.089	0.283	.197*	0.017	0.094	0.261
School Awards	0.039	0.641	0.049	0.555	-0.032	0.701	0.091	0.276	0.001	0.992	0.069	0.406

Moreover, the level of compliance on accountability and transparency was significantly correlated with the drop-out rate. The negative correlation denotes that higher compliance on accountability indicates lower drop-out rates of the school.

However, all the other principles were not found to be correlated with the schools' key performance indicators.

Conclusions

The findings from the conducted study brought the researcher to the following conclusions:

The school heads of public elementary schools in the Sixth Congressional District of Pangasinan showed high compliance along the six dimensions of the School-Based Management (SBM) Framework. This shows that public elementary schools in the district have been highly adherent to the mandate of the Department of Education in terms of SBM implementation and assessment.

Enrolment counts for the past three years were found to increase the leadership of the school heads. The school heads must be assertive in keeping enrollment numbers increasing as it entails greater MOOE allocation for the school. In addition, maintaining external stakeholders engaged in school concerns is effective in sustaining projects that support school improvement.

The level of compliance to the SBM framework was not found to be associated with learners' performance over the past three years. Meanwhile, teachers' instructional materials and research outputs enrich the resources of the school and the participation of various stakeholders in school-related endeavors. Nonetheless, their high compliance with the SBM framework was effective in mitigating drop-out rates and increasing achievement and promotion rates across the past three school years.

The researcher proposed a framework that shall go beyond the improvement of SBM implementation and towards providing a blueprint for public education.

The conclusions made by the researcher are the basis for the following recommendations:

Comprehensive training on School-Based Management framework among school heads delivered through virtual platforms for a more holistic and accessible learning experience during the new normal

Sustain the high level of compliance to the SBM framework through benchmarking on best practices and exchange of ideas for improvement of SBM implementation

Training on SBM framework among teachers that is similar to that of the school heads to boost their engagement in SBM implementation and to proactively act together with school heads in formulating solutions

Review on the criteria for distribution of SBM grants by the Department of Education to make it more inclusive and more accessible to all schools

References

- Abulencia, A. S. (2012). School-based management: A structural reform intervention. *The Normal Lights*, 6(1).
- Allawan, F. D. (2012). School's community partnership practices and stakeholders' involvement in Digos City Division. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Southern Philippines Agri-Business and Marine and Aquatic School of Technology, Matti, Digos City.
- Alvarado, E. S., Juan, S., Juan, S., & Juan, S. (2019). Constraints on school-based management compliance of public schools principals. *Open Access Library Journal*, 6(07), 1.
- Anderson, J. A. (2005). *Accountability in education*. Education Policy Series. Paris: UNESCO/International Institute for Educational Planning and International Academy of Education.
- Bautista, M., & Rose, C. (2005). *Transforming education on the ground: Fifty stories of school-based management under the Third Elementary Education Project*. Department of Education, Third Elementary Education Project.
- Bautista, M. C. R., Bernardo, A. B. I., & Ocampo, D. (2010). *When reforms don't transform: Reflections on institutional reforms in the Department of Education*. HDN research monograph 2010-01. Quezon City, Philippines: Human Development Network.
- Behrman, J. R., Deolalikar, A. B., & Soon, L.-Y. (2002). *Promoting effective schooling through education decentralization in Bangladesh, Indonesia, and Philippines*. ERD Working Paper Series No. 23, Economics and Research Department, ADB.
- Benveniste, L., & Marshall, J. (2004). *School grants and student performance: Evidence from the EQIP Project in Cambodia*. Unpublished manuscript, World Bank, Washington, DC.
- Brint, S. (2017). *Schools and societies*. California: Stanford University Press.
- Bucud, R. S. (2017). *The effects of decentralization on community participation in school-based management in the Philippines*. Unpublished thesis, RMIT University, Philippines.
- Cabardo, J. R. O. (2016). Levels of participation of the school stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities and the compliance to school-based management. *Journal of Inquiry and Action in Education*, 8(1), 81-94.
- Caldwell, B. J. (2005). *School-based management (Vol. 3)*. Paris: International Institute for Educational Planning.
- Calmorin, L., & Calmorin, M. (1996). *Method of research and thesis writing*. Quezon City: Rex Book Store.

- Chavez, D., & Doromal, A. (2018). Compliance with school-based management standards: An assessment for policy formulation. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 1(1), 55–66.
- Conley, D. T. (2013). *Roadmap to restructuring: Policies, practices and the emerging visions of schooling*. Oregon: ERIC Clearinghouse on Educational Management, University of Oregon.
- Claridge, T. (2004). *Designing social capital sensitive participation methodologies*. Working Paper, University of Queensland, Australia.
- Conyers, D. (1986). Decentralisation and development: A framework for analysis. *Community Development Journal*, 21(2), 88.
- Cromwell, S. (2016). Site-based management: Boon or boondoggle? *Education World*.
Department of Education Order No. 37, s. 2009.
Department of Education Memorandum No. 386, s. 2009.
Department of Education Order No. 8, s. 2019.
Department of Education Order No. 45, s. 2015.
Department of Education Order No. 44, s. 2015.
- Di Gropello, E. (2006). A comparative analysis of school-based management in Central America (No. 72). World Bank Publications.
- Di Gropello, E., & Marshall, J. H. (2005). Teacher effort and schooling outcomes in rural Honduras. *Incentives to Improve Teaching*, 307.
- Dominguez-Lara, S. A. (2016). Content validity using Aiken's V with confidence intervals: Contributions to Rodríguez et al. *Archivos Argentinos de Pediatría*, 114(3), e221.
- Ecija, J. D. (2020). Maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) and school-based management (SBM) performance of secondary schools in Samar Island. *LC International Journal of STEM*, 1(4), 1–14.
- Fabros, M. C. Assistance provided by private entities to elementary schools in San Pablo City, Laguna.
- Fischer, F. (2012). Participatory governance: From theory to practice. *The Oxford Handbook of Governance*, 457–471.
- Glass, G. V., & Hopkins, K. D. (1984). Inferences about the difference between means. *Statistical Methods in Education and Psychology*, 230–232.
- Isaias, P., & Issa, T. (2015). Information system development life cycle models. In *High Level Models and Methodologies for Information Systems* (pp. 21–40). Springer, New York, NY.
- Karim, S., Rodall, C. S., & Mendoza, E. C. (2004). *Transparency in education: Report card in Bangladesh: Quality schools programme in Mexico*. UNESCO, International Institute for Educational Planning.
- Khatti, N., Ling, C., & Jha, S. (2010). The effects of school-based management in the Philippines: An initial assessment using administrative data. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper* 5248.
- Koo, T. K., & Li, M. Y. (2016). A guideline of selecting and reporting intraclass correlation coefficients for reliability research. *Journal of Chiropractic Medicine*, 15(2), 155–163.
- LaRocque, N., & Boyer, M. (2007). Decentralisation of school management: Ideas from abroad. *Economic Note-Education Series*.
- Leithwood, K., & Menzies, T. (1998). Forms and effects of school-based management: A review. *Educational Policy*, 12(3), 325–346.
- Litvack, J., & Seddon, J. (Eds.). (1999). *Decentralization Briefing Notes*. World Bank Institute Working Papers; Washington, DC.
- Lubrica, P. A., Parcasio, I. G., Cuevas, J. P., Alvaro, M. N., Gallardo, A. V. G., & Batani, R. S. (2019). School-based management in Benguet, Philippines. *Mountain Journal of Science and Interdisciplinary Research*, 79(2 Supp 1), 152–163.
- Malen, B., Ogawa, R. T., & Kranz, J. (1990). What do we know about school-based management? A case study of the literature—a call for research. *Choice and Control in American Education*, 2, 289–342.
- Martin, M. (2019). The compliance to school-based management in public elementary schools. *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, 9(1), 44–56.
- Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (NORAD). (2013). *A framework for analysing participation in development*. Viewed 25 January 2017. Retrieved from Norad.
- Oswald, L. J. (2019). School-based management. *ERIC Digest*, Number 99.

- Patrinos, H. A., Barrera-Osorio, F., & Fasih, T. (2009). Decentralized decision-making in schools: The theory and evidence on school-based management. The World Bank.
- Rondinelli, D. A., Nellis, J. R., & Cheema, G. S. (1983). Decentralization in developing countries. World Bank Staff Working Paper, 581.
- Salkind, N. J. (2006). Encyclopedia of measurement and statistics. SAGE Publications.
- Shapiro, J. S., & Skoufias, E. (2006). Local but unequal? How educational decentralization stratifies schools. Unpublished manuscript, World Bank, Washington, DC.
- Taylor, M. (2011). Public policy in the community (2nd ed.). Palgrave Macmillan, New York.
- Villanueva, J. S., & Cruz, R. A. O. D. (2019). The praxis of school-based management on curriculum and learning in the Philippines. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 6(2), 89.
- World Bank. (2003). World Development Report 2004: Making services work for poor people. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- World Bank Group. (2016). Assessing school-based management in the Philippines. World Bank.
- World Bank. (2017). What is school-based management? Washington, DC: Education, Human Development Network.
- Yamane, T. (1967). Statistics: An introductory analysis (No. HA29 Y2 1967).
- Yamauchi, F. & Liu, Y. (2011). School quality, labor market imbalance and the investment in human capital: evidence from a school intervention in the Philippines. Quezon City: Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
- Yamauchi, F. (2014). An alternative estimate of school-based management impacts on students' achievements: evidence from the Philippines. The World Bank.
- Yau, H. K., & Cheng, A. L. F. (2014). Principals and teachers' perceptions of school-based management. *International Education Research*, 2(1), 44-59.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Sanny A. Ferrer

Sto. Domingo Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines